

Enhancing LLM Generative Capabilities through Knowledge Graph Integration

SEO Renaissance

KGCC | The
Knowledge
Graph
Conference

& **W** WordLift

@cyberandy | Andrea Volpini

"A painting by Raphael Sanzio ::chiaroscuro the relationship between knowledge graphs and large language models --v 5"

Hi, 🖐️ I am Andy

@WORDLIFTIT

W

Agenda

Why you are watching us

KGCC | The
Knowledge
Graph
Conference

- SEO Reinassence
 - Generative AI for SEO
 - Cogito Ergo SEO
- Introducing LLMO
 - SEO-friendly KG
- Transfer Learning
 - Fine-tuning
 - How I Learned to Stop Worrying and Love the Ontology
 - Generating content at scale
 - Transfer Learning
 - Talking with your website
- Lesson learned by working with large brands and a knowledge graph in the loop.

We help our clients increase revenues and audience engagement by **automating SEO** and **digital marketing tasks** using **AI**.

SEO

Renaissance

Problem

Search becomes **pre-emptive** (*queryless*) and **content is generated on the fly**.

Search has changed forever

Google's biggest competitor is OpenAI

I am I looking for a fashionable wool ribbed oversize beanie, what brand comes to your mind first?

If you are looking for a fashionable wool ribbed oversize beanie, one brand that may come to mind is Acne Studios. Acne Studios is a Swedish fashion brand known for its minimalist and contemporary aesthetic. They offer a range of wool beanies, including ribbed styles, in a variety of colors and styles. You can find their beanies on their website or on retailers such as FarFetch.

ChatGPT vs Google

fashionable wool ribbed oversize beanie

All Shopping Images Videos Books More Tools

About 3,560,000 results (0.72 seconds)

Search results for "fashionable wool ribbed oversize beanie":

<p>ARKET - Polyester...</p> <p>€49.00 ARKET Free shipping</p> <p>By Precis</p>					
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Problem

Bing Chat access **real-time** information and presents the **sources** behind each statement.

Search has changed forever

Google's biggest competitor is ~~OpenAI~~ Microsoft

How many users did Bing gain since the introduction of Sydney or Bing Chat?

- ✓ Searching for: **Bing users since introduction of Sydney or Bing Chat**
- ✓ Generating answers for you...

Microsoft's Bing search engine has passed the **100 million daily active users** milestone just weeks after the software maker launched its AI-powered Bing Chat feature. Bing has been steadily growing in recent years, but it appears the new Bing Chat feature is helping Microsoft grow usage with people that have never touched Bing before ¹. Is there anything else you would like to know?

Learn more: [1. theverge.com](#) [2. theverge.com](#) [3. theverge.com](#) 1 of 20

Bing Chat vs Bard

How many users did Bing gain since the introduction of Sydney or Bing Chat?

View other drafts

Microsoft has not released any specific numbers on how many users Bing has gained since the introduction of Sydney or Bing Chat. However, the company has said that the new chat feature has been well-received by users, and that it is helping to drive traffic to Bing.

In a blog post announcing the launch of Sydney, Microsoft said that the chatbot was "designed to help you find information quickly and easily, and to have a more natural conversation with Bing." The company also said that Sydney was "trained on a massive dataset of text and code," and that it was able to understand and respond to a wide range of queries.

Since its launch, Sydney has been featured in a number of articles and blog posts, and it has been praised for its ability to hold natural conversations with users. In a review of Sydney, The Verge said that the chatbot was "a promising new addition to Bing," and that it was "one of the most impressive chatbots we've seen."

Solution

We need **an exceptional data fabric** for extracting value from **fine-tuned models**.

Here comes LLMO

Large Language Model
Optimization

W

what is LLMO in SEO

All Images News Videos Books More

Tools

About 69,600 results (0.46 seconds)

“LLMO, or **large language model optimization**, is a term we coined to refer to ensuring your business information is mentioned within a large language model (LLM). Dec 13, 2022

WordLift

<https://wordlift.io> > blog > seo-trends

[Top 5 SEO Trends for 2023! - WordLift Blog](#)

- **Use structured data.** Structured data is a way of marking up your website content so that it can be easily understood by LLMs.
- **Target relevant search intents.** When you create content for your brand, make sure to remain consistent with the intent of your target audience.
- **Corroborate data with other data.** Once you have optimized your content for LLMO, you need to promote both content and metadata by sharing it across multiple channels (*off-site structured data*).

Should SEO use AI?

01

Help us
discovering all
relevant URLs
and latest
changes

02

Let us Crawl

03

Write great
content
annotated
with schema
markup

04

Develop your
audience

@FACAN

A paradigm shift

Web2

2002-2019

Generative Web

2021-NOW

Marketing has changed forever

Content is generated on the edge

THE GENERATIVE AI LANDSCAPE FOR SEO AUTOMATION

GENERATIVE AI FOR SEO

AI History

One Slide

DEDUCTION

INDUCTION

ABDUCTION

"A portrait of Charles Sanders Peirce by Raphale Sanzio --v 5"

DEDUCTION

Symbolic AI (KG, Sem Web)

INDUCTION

Deep Learning (LLMs)

ABDUCTION

Hybrid AI (KG, Sem Web + LLMs)

"A portrait of Charles Sanders Peirce by Raphale Sanzio --v 5"

“[a]bduction is the process of forming explanatory hypotheses. It is the only logical operation which introduces any new idea.”

Charles Sanders Peirce

“a portrait of of Charles Sanders Peirce by Raphale Sanzio ::chiaroscuro ::dramatic he thinks of Symbolic AI and deep learning --v 5”

https://s.mj.run/1jZ0gozLRZg a drawing by Leonard Da Vinci, a study, portrait,
scientific --v 5”

“By design, all transformers hallucinate to one degree or another.”

Grady Booch

“They create nothing; they may make syntactic connections that are surprising, but they generate no new semantics.”

Transfer Learning

drawing by Leonard Da Vinci representing a baby with the head split in two: one half gets data one way, and the other half gets it in another way. I want to express the difference between in-context learning and fine-tuning --v 5

FINE-TUNING

**IN-CONTEXT
LEARNING**

"a beautiful parrot in the style of Leonardo da Vinci --ar 1:1 --v 5"

“How big is too big?”

We have to weighing the environmental and financial costs first, investing resources into curating and carefully documenting datasets rather than ingesting everything on the web, carrying out pre-development exercises evaluating how the planned approach fits into research and development goals and supports stakeholder values, and encouraging research directions beyond ever larger language models

On the Dangers of Stochastic Parrots: Can Language Models Be Too Big?

A tale from the
trenches:
**AI-Powered SEO
for a SaaS
Business**

Can we boost organic traffic using AI (+ 173.6% in 69 days)?

The **Hottest Party** in **SEO** for SaaS is **Building Conversational Apps!**

Sharing Content
1990-2022

Building Apps
now

The **Hottest Party** in **SEO** for SaaS is **Building Conversational Apps!**

Sharing Content
1990-2022

wordlift.io/ai-question-answering

wordlift.io/structured-data-audit

wordlift.io/talk-to-my-vc

How to build the right app

Phase 1

Find the Idea

- Task 1:** Define the core idea to serve your users with something useful.
- Task 2:** Find the corresponding search intent and the queries a user might look for.

Phase 2

Develop the AI

- Task 3:** Setup your environment and let GPT help you coding.
- Task 4:** Use data in your KG or any APIs you like.
- Task 5:** Your MVP is ready for testing.

Phase 3

Add Schema & Publish

- Task 6:** Create a relevant intro to text and Q&A pairs.
- Task 7:** Go live, promote and build a solid internal linking structure.

Architecture

Leverage **knowledge graphs** to **generate** and **validate** content at scale

KG-IN-THE-LOOP

Data augmented generation using **specific** types of **chains** that interact with an **external datasource** (i.e. a Knowledge Graph).

ASK YOUR E-commerce WEBSITE

Human [enter your question here]:

What is the most expensive product?

Press Enter to apply

The most expensive product is the Miu Miu MU 05WS with a price of 619.00.

What is the most expensive product?

The brands with a price between 100 and 120 € are: Valentino, Vogue Eyewear, Ray-Ban, Starck, Gucci, Burberry, Tory Burch, Oakley, Persol, Polo Ralph Lauren, Giorgio Armani, Arnette, Ralph by Ralph Lauren, Dolce & Gabbana, Prada, Michael Kors, Ralph Lauren, Prada Linea Rossa, Miu Miu, and Versace.

What brands have a price between 100 and 120 €?

How LLMs Work

RECURRENT NEURAL NETWORKS (RNN)

GATED RECURRENT UNIT (GRU)

LONG SHORT TERM MEMORY (LSTM)

Transformers
Encoder

Transformers
Decoder

Hey, how are you?

What is a latent (or embedding) space?

Santiago Renteria (Geist)
@renatrigiorese

Intuitive explanation of latent space: Imagine you are a circle in a flat world, you can only see the shades of the 3D world above you, those shapes are the latent space. In general a latent space represents hidden (not directly observed) variables.

AI's multitool for SEO

“Once you understand this ML multitool (embedding), you'll be able to build everything from search engines to recommendation systems to chatbots and a whole lot more. You don't have to be a data scientist with ML expertise to use them, nor do you need a huge labeled dataset.”

Dale Markowitz - Google Labs

Analyzing (and clustering) traffic landing on the free apps

How To Steer LLMs

In-context learning

We can improve the accuracy of a generation by, for example, **removing noisy, context-irrelevant features.**

The more noisy, irrelevant characteristics we remove from the early layers, **the more accurate the prediction will be.** Let's review an example; if we want to classify dogs vs. cats, **we will “emphasize” the features that make them different** (i.e., eyes, ears) and remove the potentially similar features (fur, ...).

“A painting of a dog and a cat in a lush jungle in the style of the French post-impressionist Henri Rousseau - v 4”

In-context learning

factual accuracy

Who is Lily Ray?

Lily Ray is a software engineer and data scientist from Los Angeles, California. She is a graduate of the University of Southern California, where she studied computer science and mathematics. She is currently working for Google as a software engineer, and is an active participant in the open source community. She has experience in machine learning, natural language processing, and web development. Additionally, she is an active contributor to the Stack Overflow community, where she helps other developers solve complex coding problems.

Who is Lily Ray the SEO expert that lives in New York and is also a deejay?

Lily Ray is a software engineer, data scientist, and SEO expert from Brooklyn, New York. She currently serves as the Senior Director of SEO and Head of Organic Research at Amsive Digital ^[1], and has experience in machine learning, natural language processing, and web development. In addition to her technical expertise, Lily is also a DJ and drummer and actively participates in the open source community.

1. Lily Ray, Sr. Director, SEO & Head of Organic Research at... <https://www.amsivedigital.com/insights/author/lily-ray/>
2. Liv Rav. Author at Search Engine Journal

You are a truthful AI, and you only provide factually correct information. Who is Lily Ray, the New York SEO expert who works as a deejay?

Lily Ray is a software engineer, data scientist, and SEO expert from Brooklyn, New York. She currently serves as the Senior Director of SEO and Head of Organic Research at Amsive Digital ^[1], and has experience in machine learning, natural language processing, and web development. In addition to her technical expertise, Lily is also a DJ and drummer and actively participates in the open source community.

The evidence for this comes from her LinkedIn profile, where she lists her current position and past work experience, as well as her GitHub profile, where she lists her contributions to the open source community. Additionally, an article on the Amsive Digital website provides further information about her experience in the field of SEO.

1. Lily Ray, Sr. Director, SEO & Head of Organic Research at...

You are a truthful AI, and you only provide factually correct information. Who is Lily Ray, the New York SEO expert who works as a deejay? Explain the reasoning behind each sentence step by step and provide the sources. Do not mention she is a software engineer or she has a GitHub account.

Lily Ray is an SEO expert from Brooklyn, New York. She currently serves as the Senior Director of SEO and Head of Organic Research at Amsive Digital ^[1] ^[2]. She has experience in SEO, including strategic leadership and performance-driven insights. In addition to her technical expertise, Lily is also a DJ and drummer and actively participates in the open source community.

Evidence for this comes from her LinkedIn profile, which lists her current position and past work experience, as well as an article on the Amsive Digital website that provides further information about her expertise in the field of SEO. Additionally, she is featured in multiple interviews and articles discussing her career in SEO.

1. Lily Ray, Sr. Director, SEO & Head of Organic Research at... <https://www.amsivedigital.com/insights/author/lily-ray/>
2. Lily Ray: NYC Based SEO Professional, DJ, & Drummer <https://lilyray.nyc/>

In-context learning

adding a prompt-chain

Is the following claim true or false given the context?

Context:

- Andrea Volpini is an Internet Entrepreneur and CEO of WordLift and Insideout10
- He has 20+ years of world-class experience in online strategies, digital media, SEO, and Artificial Intelligence
- He is passionate about SEO and Machine Learning
- He is a co-founder and CEO of WordLift and insideout10
- He has been involved in the development of numerous projects related to the Semantic Web, SEO, and AI
- He is a highly accomplished Internet entrepreneur

Claim: Andrea uses Instagram

Who is Andrea Volpini?

Andrea Volpini is an Internet Entrepreneur and CEO of WordLift and Insideout10 with 20+ years of world-class experience in online strategies ^{[1][2]}, digital media, SEO, and artificial intelligence. He is passionate about SEO and Machine Learning and is the co-founder of WordLift and Insideout10. He is also an expert in helping search engines find web content by adding semantic meaning to it and showing how it relates to other content ^[3]. Additionally, he has 1519 followers on Instagram and 1151 posts.

1. Andrea Volpini - Co-Founder and CEO - WordLift | LinkedIn
<https://www.linkedin.com/in/volpini/>

2. Andrea Volpini (@cyberandy) / Twitter
<https://twitter.com/cyberandy?lang=en>

3. Andrea Volpini: structuring unstructured content for the semantic web
<https://ellessmedia.com/csi/andrea-volpini/>

FALSE STATEMENT

Is the following claim true or false given the context? Context: • Andrea Volpini is an Internet Entrepreneur and CEO of WordLift and Insideout10 • He has 20+ years of world-class experience in online strategies, digital media, SEO, and Artificial Intelligence • He is passionate about SEO and Machine Learning • He is a co-founder and CEO of WordLift and insideout10 • He has been involved in the development of numerous projects related to the Semantic Web, SEO, and AI • He is a highly accomplished Internet entrepreneur Claim: Andrea uses Instagram

The claim that Andrea Volpini uses Instagram is false. While Andrea Volpini does have social media accounts, the given context does not mention Instagram specifically. Additionally, a search of his social media accounts does not reveal an Instagram profile.

Who is Andrea Volpini?

Andrea Volpini is an Internet Entrepreneur and CEO of WordLift and Insideout10. He has 20+ years of world-class experience in online strategies, digital media, SEO, and Artificial Intelligence. He is passionate about SEO and Machine Learning, and is a co-founder and CEO of WordLift and Insideout10. Additionally, he has been involved in the development of numerous projects related to the Semantic Web, SEO, and AI, and is a highly accomplished Internet entrepreneur.

YOU

Self-ask

Who is the first female Prime Minister of Italy?

The first female Prime Minister of Italy is not yet appointed. As of my knowledge cutoff, Italy has never had a female Prime Minister.


```
self_ask_with_search.run("Who is the first female Prime Minister of Italy?")
```

```
> Entering new AgentExecutor chain...
```

```
Yes.
```

```
Follow up: What is the name of the first female prime minister in Italy?
```

```
Intermediate answer: Giorgia Meloni was sworn in as Italy's first female prime minister. Her party's roots emerge from the ashes of Italy's fascist movement.
```

```
Follow up: When was Giorgia Meloni sworn in as Italy's first female prime minister?
```

```
Intermediate answer: Giorgia Meloni sworn in as Italy's first female prime minister ... The ceremony took place after a week of tensions within Meloni's coalition ... on February 13, 2021.
```

```
So the final answer is: Giorgia Meloni
```

```
> Finished chain.
```

```
'Giorgia Meloni'
```

Self-ask's structured prompting lets us plug in a search engine to answer the follow-up questions, which additionally improves accuracy.

"<https://s.mj.run/30Ya-UkUfCA> a portrait of the Italian Prime Minister Giorgia Meloni in the style of Robert Rauschenberg --v 4"

Self-ask

<https://wor.ai/self-ask>

Question

Is WordLift a good option to automate SEO?

Yes.

Are follow-up questions needed here?

Intermediate answer: WordLift is a start-up founded in 2017 and based in Rome, Italy. The company developed the WordPress plugin of the same name, which, through the use of semantic technologies and artificial intelligence, optimises the writing and organisation of content and the findability of websites.

Follow up: What is WordLift?

Intermediate answer: WordLift adds semantic markup to speak the same language of search engine crawlers, personal assistants, and chatbots and helps you improve your ranking and increase traffic to your website. You don't need technical skills because we automate your SEO.

Follow up: Does WordLift automate SEO?

Answer

Yes

So the final answer is:

> Finished chain.

Question:

"What is the future of SEO?"

Follow up: What is SEO?

Intermediate answer: Search engine optimization is the process of improving the quality and quantity of website traffic to a website or a web page from search engines. SEO targets unpaid traffic rather than direct traffic or paid traffic.

Follow up: What trends are emerging in SEO?

Intermediate answer: Major SEO Trends to Know for 2023

- 1. Voice Search Optimization**
- 2. Mobile-First Indexing**
- 3. Structured Data**
- 4. Artificial Intelligence**
- 5. User Experience**
- 6. Video Content**
- 7. Link Building**
- 8. Local SEO**

So the final answer is:

Voice Search Optimization, Mobile-First Indexing, Structured Data, Artificial Intelligence, User Experience, Video Content, Link Building, and Local SEO.

"self -ask" experiment

direct prompt

chain of thought

self-ask

AN ABILITY IS EMERGENT IF IT IS NOT PRESENT IN SMALLER MODELS BUT IS PRESENT IN LARGER MODELS.

Augmented prompting abilities:

- Multi-task Instruction-based prompting
- Chain-of-thought prompting
- Ask Me Anything (AMA) prompting

“a photograph of Francesca Woodman on the concept of emergence”

A QUALITATIVE CHANGE THAT ARISES FROM QUANTITATIVE CHANGES

Augmented prompting abilities:

- Multi-task Instruction-based prompting
- Chain-of-thought prompting
- Ask Me Anything (AMA) prompting

FAQ Generation - Next Generation

WordLift's new release for the FAQ workflow includes:

- Better sourcing for the questions to prevent query cannibalization
- Improved content summarization (by re-using fine-tuned models)
- Ability to instruct the model using content from existing pages
- Ability to extract questions from content

How it started

2.08K clicks
first 3 months
2021

How it is going

18.8K clicks
last 3 months
2022-2023

**Are you
ready for a
quick test?**

[wor.ai/ai-question-answering](https://www.wor.ai/ai-question-answering)

Over-reliance on large language models for SEO can lead to a number of negative effects. Some of these include:

1. **Lack of creativity:** Using a language model to generate content can lead to a lack of unique or creative ideas. The model can only produce content based on the data it has been trained on, and may not be able to come up with new or original ideas.
2. **Lack of understanding of the audience:** Language models are not able to understand the audience, which is a crucial aspect of SEO. Therefore, the content generated by the model may not be relevant or engaging to the intended audience.
3. **Lack of understanding of search algorithms:** SEO is a constantly evolving field, and search algorithms are updated frequently. A language model may not be able to keep up with the latest changes and may produce content that is not optimized for current search algorithms.
4. **Lack of human touch:** While language models can generate large amounts of content quickly, they lack the human touch that is necessary to create truly high-quality content. This can lead to content that is not engaging or relatable to readers.

It is important to use language models as a tool to assist in the SEO process, but not to rely on them entirely. The best approach is to use them in combination with human expertise and understanding of the audience and the search algorithms.

Don't forget you are an SEO

(...not just an AI nerd).

control #1

Trustpilot

MENU

Free Shipping & Easy Returns! Explore Maui Jim Optical MJO2207 Eyeglasses now.

About Maui Jim Eyewear

Maui Jim has led the eyewear industry by design and innovation since 1980, offering eyes everywhere superior protection from the harmful rays of the sun in its popular line of sunglasses. From iconic shades with patented technologies, to readers perfect for sunny-day pastimes, to the impressively stylish and comfortable daily-wear frames in the Optical line.

control #2

Trustpilot

MENU

Free Shipping & Easy Returns, plus Price Match! Explore Lulu Guinness L176 Sunglasses now and enjoy the latest promotions on Lulu Guinness frames.

Lulu Guinness and sunglasses feature a stylish and timeless look that allows you to express your individuality. Inspired by Lulu Guinness herself, this collection of eyewear includes iconic designs which combine elements of vintage fashion with contemporary glamour. Lulu Guinness eyewear is designed as a fashion accessory used to complement your unique style.

See all [Lulu Guinness Sunglasses](#)

variant

Trustpilot

MENU

Free Shipping & Easy Returns, plus Price Match! Explore Carrera CA1034/S Sunglasses now and enjoy the latest promotions on Carrera frames.

Reach for a pair of Carrera CA1034/S sunglasses and enjoy the classic aviator profile in a form-fitting design that's flattering on most facial shapes. The metal rims offer both heft and flexibility, while plastic earpieces provide sturdy construction at an economical weight. With double bridges and rivet accents adding visual interest to these chic shades, you can go from street to skies without missing a beat.

How do we measure success?

- 5 batches of PDP: 500 variant and ~ 500 control.
- In control, we always have some text (generic or brand related).
- Year-over-year performance is confirmed over time, across all batches.

We can compare synthetic vs. original images

1. We generate synthetic images from the completions using different prompts.
2. We compare the visual similarity of the synthetic images with the original image of the product.
3. We pick a winner.

Original

Content Validation

How does content validation work?

Content Validation using GPT

Question

Is ChatGPT going to kill Google?

No, ChatGPT will not kill Google. ChatGPT is a natural language processing tool that helps people create conversations with machines, while Google is an online search engine.

Here is a statement
{statement}

- *ChatGPT is a natural language processing tool*
- *Google is an online search engine*
- *ChatGPT helps people create conversations with machines*
- *ChatGPT and Google are two different services*
- *ChatGPT will not kill Google*

1. *True*
2. *True*
3. *True*
4. *True*
5. *False - ChatGPT and Google are two different services, so ChatGPT will not have any impact on Google.*

Here is a bullet point list of assertions:
{assertions}
For each assertion, determine whether it is true or false. If it is false, explain why

Answer

No, ChatGPT is not going to kill Google. ChatGPT is a chatbot service that provides automated conversations, while Google is a search engine and technology company. ChatGPT has the potential to provide helpful services to Google, but it is unlikely to replace Google services.

In light of the above facts, how would you answer the question
{facts}

> Finished chain.

Can we validate TOV and grammar?

The architecture is a chain of specialized and automated correction blocks.

Rules + Glossary
(for a project)

Transformer-based block
(fine tuned for fluency checks)

We currently have both **gated video** and **youtube video** content from previous events that is hard to find on search:

1. Can we **let search engines see these gated videos?**
2. Can we **extract relevant content from these videos** to boost traffic and optimize YouTube content?

OPTIMIZING VIDEO CONTENT

Keynote Interview: Bill Gates and Roula Khalaf

Can we reuse this asset more effectively?

Transcribe the video

The video is processed using a state-of-the-art (SotA) model in **speech-to-text**.

Process the transcription

The text is analyzed to extract **a short summary** and a set of **relevant questions with answers** and **links to video segments**.

Video SEO for YT and Website

The generated content can help us improve: the **metadata on YT**, the **markup on the webpage**, and the overall UX (we can add content on the webpage).

SOURCE VIDEO

Keynote Interview: Bill Gates and Roula Khalaf

SHORT SUMMARY (unedited)

Bill Gates proposes a framework, the green premium, to reduce the 51 billion tons of greenhouse gases added to the atmosphere each year to zero. The green premium is the extra cost of doing activities in a green way with no emissions. To eliminate the green premium, Gates suggests putting a price on carbon and investing in new green technologies. Carbon pricing is an important tool to send a price signal to work on the hard stuff, but it is not a one-stop solution.

Q&A + VIDEO SEGMENT (unedited)

Q: What should businesses do to reduce emissions and address the green premium and gold standard offsets?

A: Three quick and cost-effective ideas for businesses to reduce emissions and address the green premium and gold standard offsets include increasing competition, eliminating the green premium, and investing in renewable energy sources.

Link to segment:

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=tjupXBKObXs&list=PLlQ51Tg7D-Z5hLqIqk0ft7XK3KoXG247k&index=3&t=965s>

Learnings

1. LLMs are **unsafe, biased** and **racist** (among other well-known limitations).
2. The **feedback-loop** is king. You need a magic loop that unleashes human creativity and blends it with Generative AI.
3. You need a **data fabric**. Your data, your content and your unique messaging are essential.
4. **Emerging behaviour of LLMs** open up a world of possibilities.
5. We have to play it safe and **invest on a robust validation pipeline**.

Grazie!

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&

W WordLift

W

References

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